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ATTITUDE OF TET AMONG B.ED. STUDENT- TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Teacher Eligibility Test is an Indian entrance examination for teachers. The test is mandatory for getting teaching jobs in government schools from Class 1 to Class 8. Paper 1 is meant for teachers opting for Class 1 to Class 5 and Paper 2 for Class 6 to Class 8. It is conducted by both Central government and State governments in India. Most states conduct their own TET. The present study focused on the positive and negative attitudes towards TET examination. For this purpose, this research was conducted with 500 student teachers in survey method. A self-made tool consists of 27 items. The findings of this study brought into light some vital reasons behind the attitudes exhibited by the teachers regarding TET, was mainly due to the importance of TET, its necessity, and the problems faced by the teachers while attending TET. On the basis of the findings it is suggested that, as the test is mandatory for getting teaching jobs in government schools, all the opportunities, resources and facilities should be given to the student teachers during their B.Ed. course for their professional development and to fulfill and achieve educational goals. It is necessary to ensure teachers with the essential aptitude and ability to meet the challenges of teaching at the primary and upper primary level.

Keywords:

Teacher Eligibility Test, TET examination, teaching.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education has initially been the responsibility of the family and ultimately the society. Society entrusted this responsibility to school and to run schools the teachers are the indispensable need of it. The development and growth are all depend upon education that is provided. The central and state government is planning to develop the skill and quality manpower in development like medicine, science, technology and education etc. Education is a process by which people acquire knowledge, skills, habits values or attitude.

2. TEACHER ELIGIBILITY TEST

The Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) which will be conducted by the appropriate Government. The rationale for including the TET as a minimum qualification for a person to be eligible for appointment is as under. It would bring national standards and benchmark of teacher quality in the recruitment process. It would induce teacher education institutions and students for these institutions to further improve their performance standards It would send a positive signal to all stakeholders that the government lays special emphasis on teacher quality. The TET examination may be conducted by the suitable professional body designated by the appropriate Government for the purpose. It will be conducted in accordance with the Guidelines

3. NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The NCERT has decided to improve the quality in teacher education by Conducting CTET and it recommends to state governments to conduct the eligibility test at state. The primary aim of CTET and TET are to make quality teacher education and reducing the jobless teachers. This study is used to know the attitude of the student teachers towards TET examination. So, the investigator of the study has taken the topic as “Attitude of TET among B.Ed. Student-Teachers”.

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out the significant difference between the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Gender
- To find out the significant difference between the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.
- To find out the significant difference between the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Medium of Instruction.

5. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Gender
- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.
- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Medium of Instruction.

6. METHODOLOGY

For the present study survey method had been adopted.

SAMPLE

The investigator used convenient sampling technique in non-probability sampling technique and chosen as many as 500 B.Ed. student-teachers in Coimbatore district.

TOOL

In the present study the investigator has constructed and standardized a tool to measure the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards teacher eligibility test. The tool was framed as Likert-type scale and each statement is set against a five-point scale of “strongly agree”, “agree”, “neutral”, “disagree”, “strongly disagree” and the scoring response for positive statements is 5,4,3,2,1 and scoring is reversed for negative statements. The final tool consists of 27 statements and all statements are favorable to the variable or study.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data was collected by the investigator using the tool developed for this purpose. All the data were collected by the investigator.

Table 1: There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Gender

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - Value
Boys	117.21	9.72	0.40
Girls	117.62	11.26	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (0.40) greater than the table value (1.96) for 0.05 level of significance.

Table 2: There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - Value
Urban	116.3275	11.6559	8.223193
Rural	122.25.62	4.231615	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (8.22) greater than the table value (1.96) for 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3: There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Medium of Instruction.

Groups	Mean	Standard Deviation	t - Value
Tamil	115.24	11.69	2.95
English	118.50	10.33	

The significant of the mean difference is tested using t – test from the above table. It is clear that the calculated t – value (2.95) greater than the table value (1.96) for 0.05 level of significance.

7. DISCUSSION AND FINDING

The main objective of this study is to find out the knowledge of XI standard students. The data were analyzed by applying descriptive and inferential statistics. Out of the 4 hypothesis, 2 hypotheses were accepted and the remaining 2 were rejected.

- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Gender
- There is significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.
- There is significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TamilNadu Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Medium of Instruction.

8. CONCLUSION

TET syllabus is in B.Ed. course in the name of professional course for teacher proficiency in Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University in Tamil Nadu, India. It is importance and the urgent need of professional development of teachers and student teachers at present. The main purpose of this study was to gain an in-depth understanding of the attitude of the student teachers in B.ED toward TET. The findings of this study brought into light some vital reasons behind the attitudes exhibited by the student teachers regarding TET, was mainly due to the importance of TET, its necessity, and the problems faced by the student teachers while attending TET. On the basis of the findings it is suggested that, as the test is mandatory for getting teaching jobs in government schools, all the opportunities, resources and facilities should be given to the student teachers during their B.Ed. course for their professional development and to fulfill and achieve educational goals. It is necessary to ensure teachers with the essential aptitude and ability to meet the challenges of teaching at the primary and upper primary level.

9. REFERENCES

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